

The Effects of the New Coronavirus Disease (Covid 19) on Human Psychology and its Financial Negatives

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Abstract

With the Covid-19 pandemic causing prolonged exposure to stress, researchers have taken an increased interest in social and societal rest to psychologically support the. While this increased attention can help manage the current situation and other epidemics and pandemics, the security measures taken in the management of the pandemic have had different consequences for individuals depending on the social role invested. Some segments of the population are more at risk of anxious, depressed, and post-traumatic symptoms as they are more susceptible to stress. This article focuses on two issues: (1) psychological issues of affected people as well as psychological approaches to unaffected people; and (2) assessing the economic impacts of the pandemic and the virus. For example, telepsychology is a valid tool that is effective in taking responsibility for the psychological suffering caused by the pandemic and preventing the disease from becoming chronic. Long-term stress can include anxiety, depression, and an inability to manage traumatic and negative emotions. In addition, the constant fear of contagion affects daily life and changes human relationships, leading to social isolation. Covid 19 first appeared in Wuhan, China on December 12, 2019, and became the number one agenda of the world after China was notified to the World Health Organization (WHO) on December 31, and the first loss of life was experienced on January 11 , 2020. Coronaviruses are a large family of viruses that can cause illness in animals or humans.

Keywords: *Psychological effects of coronavirus, Economic effects of coronavirus, Coronavirus and human psychology, Coronavirus, pandemic with human psychology and economic effects*

1. Introduction

The recommended ways and national-international measures to reduce the spread of the virus have completely changed our daily lives. Schools were closed, many businesses were temporarily closed, sports events were postponed, cinemas and theaters were closed. There was a situation where we couldn't go out unless we had to.

People Most Affected by the Disease:

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- a. *those over 60*
- b. *People with serious chronic medical conditions:*
- c. *Heart disease*
- d. *Hypertension*
- e. *Diabetes*
- f. *chronic respiratory disease*
- g. *like cancer*
- h. *Health workers*

The basic principles recommended to reduce the overall risk of transmission of acute respiratory infections also apply to Novel Coronavirus Disease (COVID-19).

2. These;

- a. *Attention should be paid to hand hygiene. Hands should be washed with soap and water for at least 20 seconds, and alcohol-based hand sanitizer should be used when soap and water are not available. There is no need to use antiseptic or antibacterial soap, normal soap is sufficient.*
- b. *Mouth, nose and eyes should not be touched without washing hands. Avoid contact with sick people (at least 1 m away if possible). Hands should be cleaned frequently, especially after direct contact with sick people or their environment . Due to the high presence of patients, health centers should not be visited if possible, and contact with other patients should be minimized when it is necessary to go to a health institution.*
- c. *When coughing or sneezing, the nose and mouth should be covered with disposable tissue paper, in the absence of tissue paper, the inside of the elbow should be used, if possible, crowded places should not be entered, if it is necessary to enter, the mouth and nose should be covered, and a medical mask should be used.*

- d. *Eating raw or undercooked animal products should be avoided. Well-cooked foods should be preferred.*
- e. *Areas of high risk for common infections, such as farms, livestock markets and areas where animals may be slaughtered, should be avoided.*
- f. *If any respiratory symptoms occur within 14 days after the trip, the nearest health institution should be applied by wearing a mask, and the doctor should be informed about the travel history.*

3. What are the Psychological Effects of Coronavirus?

With the new type of coronavirus (Covid-19) becoming an epidemic in the world, the physiological effect of the virus and methods of protection began to be mentioned frequently. However, with the increase in coronavirus cases, in addition to the physiological effects, there are also psychological effects in humans. The recommended ways and national-international measures to reduce the spread of the virus have completely changed our daily lives. Schools were closed, many businesses were temporarily closed, sports events were postponed, cinemas and theaters were closed. There was a situation where we couldn't go out unless we had to. It can be difficult to adapt to these new conditions, where everyone has to stay at home, and to get through this process without any problems. The psychological effects of the coronavirus can be seen in both adults and children. In this process, the relationships of parents with their children, how they explain the virus and how they manage this process will also be effective in the psychology of children.

1. What Psychological Problems Can Coronavirus Cause?

a. Anxiety Disorder (Anxiety)

One of the psychological problems that may arise in this situation is anxiety. The fact that there is a new and unpredictable virus that has taken the whole world under its influence causes fear and anxiety. The fact that new numbers are reported every day and false information is circulating increases this fear and panic situation. The main reason for this fear is that scientists can gradually reveal new information about the coronavirus, uncertainty continues, and the

rapid spread of the virus. However, this fear and panic will not only reduce the defense against the disease, but also trigger anxiety (anxiety disorder).

b. Depression

Another psychological problem caused by the coronavirus is depression. The obligation to stay home and stay away from activities that will make you feel loved, happy and peaceful can lead people to a depressive mood. People can turn into someone who cannot enjoy life because of this depressed mood. Not being able to reach the life routine they need, being isolated from life and not being able to socialize can cause depression.

c. Obsessive compulsive disorder

The most recommended measure to protect from coronavirus is to pay attention to cleanliness and maintain social distance. However, being overly meticulous in these situations can also harm you. There was a situation where people were constantly washing or washing their hands. This can lead to increases in obsessive compulsive disorder, which is popularly known as obsession. The increase in obsessive compulsive disorder can cause both psychological and physiological harm to people. You may spend most of the day washing and washing hands. This may also cause your skin to become irritated, weaken the protective barrier of the skin, and break the body's resistance.

2. What Can Be Done Against the Psychological Effects of Coronavirus?

a. Follow Trusted Sources

Follow the precautions recommended by the World Health Organization and the Ministry of Health against the coronavirus. Don't leave the house unless you have to. You can minimize your fear by being informed and taking the necessary precautions. The increase in your anxiety and fear causes you to perceive many other things more negatively. Therefore, stay away from people and sources that will increase your fear. Do not follow people and publications that do not know about the subject. If you think you have a lack of information right now, if there are things you want to learn, learn them from reliable sources (WHO and Ministry of Health shares).

b. Don't Read News About the Subject Constantly

Do not constantly research or follow news about coronavirus. Use social media intermittently. Looking at the news and social media posts on the subject at intervals of 6-8 hours will allow you to use your time more efficiently and reduce your anxiety. But excessive avoidance of the news (not looking at the news at all) can also be harmful. Increasing uncertainty about the virus in your mind can increase anxiety and cause panic.

c. Continue Your Routine

Listen to the agenda other than the virus. In order to manage your fear, you need to be able to lead a normal life. Try to maintain your routine at home. You can read a book, watch a movie, and do exercises at home. You can play games and do activities with your children. Spending this process on social media or technological devices harms both children and adults. Keep in touch with your relatives, communicate, maintain social relations (by maintaining social distance), be in sharing.

3. When to Get Psychological Support?

Necessary anxiety and fear will lead you to take precautions. However, if anxiety and fear cause eating disorders, sleep disorders, and nightmares about the epidemic, it is a sign that the psychology of the person is negatively affected.

Being unable to forget thoughts about the coronavirus, constantly following research and news about the virus/disease may lead to impairments in functionality. If early measures are not taken against these situations, it will be more difficult for individuals to cope with the psychological effects of the coronavirus in the future.

If individuals pay attention to hygiene to the extent that they harm themselves, sleep and eating disorders have started, if there is a panic situation that will reduce functionality, psychological support should be sought.

4. How to Explain the Coronavirus to Children?

- a. 1. *First of all, it is necessary to protect children from false information that can be learned from the environment and social media.*
- b. 2. *Children should be given enlightening information on the subject in accordance with their age and developmental period.*
- c. 3. *Children should be taught how to protect themselves.*
- d. 4. *The child should be told that he can ask the questions in his mind to his parents and communication should be kept open.*
- e. 5. *The questions that the child will ask should be answered honestly in accordance with the developmental period.*
- f. *In order not to worry the child, wrong or evasive answers should not be given.*
- g. 6. *As parents worry, children worry too. So avoid worrying behavior and conversations.*
- h. 7. *Do not make scary speeches so that he can apply the measures to protect against the coronavirus.*
- i. 8. *Being overly insistent on cleaning and being intimidated can cause other problems. It is necessary to give cleaning training without exaggeration or obsession, emphasizing that hygiene rules are always important for us. Explain how to wash your hands, how to cover your mouth when coughing or sneezing.*

5. Financial Negatives:

It appeared in Thailand two days after the first loss of life in China, five days later in Japan, nine days later in S. Korea, ten days later in the USA, 14 days later in France, Canada and Malaysia. Within four months, it spread all over the world.

Production has been greatly reduced in all sectors except for the sectors where a limited number of goods and services are produced, such as masks, gloves, colognes, respirators, protective overalls, cleaning products, some electronic devices, cargo, courier, information communication networks and social media, the use of which has increased due to the epidemic. There were no activities in the sectors of transportation, tourism, hotel management, restaurants and events (congress, conference, cinema, theatre, concert, wedding, engagement etc.) for months.

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Football league matches were first canceled and then it was accepted to be played without spectators. Many of the companies operating in the manufacturing industry had to cut their production to a large extent.

Formal education has turned into distance education, shopping malls have been closed to shopping, Kaaba and mosques have been closed for months, Hajj and Umrah programs for 2020 have been canceled all over the world.

In many countries, people could not leave their homes for weeks in order to protect themselves from the epidemic; Even those who have to work compulsorily due to their jobs, such as health workers, security guards, bakers, have been restricted. Those who leave their homes were asked to wear masks and not to approach each other more than 1-2 meters depending on the risk of contamination.

A curfew was imposed several times on weekends. The curfews of people over 65 and younger than 20 have been restricted for months across Turkey. Restrictions in the agricultural sector were partially loosened in order not to experience food shortage problems in the event of an extended period of the epidemic.

Markets were tried to be kept open in order to prevent the spread of the epidemic caused by the crowds that were formed by the people's attack on the markets, and restaurants were allowed to serve outside in the form of takeaway. During the course of the epidemic in 2020, sometimes pessimism and sometimes optimism increased. From the point of view of the Northern Hemisphere, when the epidemic that spread to the world in winter and spring seasons slowed down in summer, optimism increased. However, in the autumn of 2020, the epidemic returned more severely and pessimism increased.

Vaccine news from the USA, Germany and China in November and December raised the optimism again and countries entered the race to supply vaccines. This optimism was again shattered by the news from England that Covid 19 had mutated and the new virus was spreading 70% faster. Many countries have restricted travel to the UK.

World Health Organization emergency team leader Dr. According to Mike Ryan, the Covid-19 outbreak is a warning of possible larger outbreaks.

It is not the biggest of the epidemic. Similar dangers will continue to exist. To act together in this process; It is important to understand the importance of cooperation in science,

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procurement, education, management and communication (BBC Turkish, 2021). It has gained importance what measures can be taken to alleviate the devastating economic effects of the Covid 19 epidemic and possible future epidemics and to allow the Turkish economy to catch up with developed countries in the long run.

For this purpose, the study will continue under the headings of the devastating economic effects of Covid 19 and the need for transformation in the Turkish economy. Human deaths caused by Covid 19 will be obtained from the worldometer website, which publishes comprehensive and up-to-date statistics on this subject, and other data will be obtained from the IMF, TurkStat, CBRT, Ministry of Treasury and Finance, Bureau of Labor Statistics and Statistics Time websites. The theoretical literature on the need for transformation in the Turkish economy will be used. 2. The Destructive Economic Effects of Covid 19 Covid 19 has taken its place among major epidemics in terms of human deaths, economic losses and horrors in humans.

The magnitude of the horror stemmed from the development of communication channels, the helplessness of humanity in the face of the epidemic in the age of science, and the fact that people acquired greater wealth than in the past. As wealth increased, people got used to luxury life, the desire to live and the fear of dying due to the epidemic increased.

While analyzing the devastating effects of Covid 19 on the Turkish economy, the conditions of the Turkish economy before Covid 19 should not be overlooked.

As it will be remembered, Turkey's relations with the USA and the EU were strained after the Fetö coup attempt on 15 July 2016. Turkey insisted that the US extradite the putschist Fetullah Gülen, but the US did not agree to this. The EU continued to host the putschists who took refuge in it. The USA also demanded the release of Priest Branson, whom Turkey had arrested on the grounds that he was a spy.

When US President Trump sent a tweet targeting the Turkish economy on August 10, 2018, in response to the detention of the priest, the dollar rate increased from 5.3 TL in the free market to 7.2 TL on the same day.

Turkey's stance in the Syrian civil war and its purchase of the S400 missile system from Russia have also led to strained relations with the United States.

President Trump sent a letter out of diplomatic courtesy to President Recep Tayyip Erdogan on September 9, 2019, when Operation Peace Spring began. Turkey did not accept this letter and returned it to itself.

The unemployment rate is over 13% and the current account deficit continues.

The conditions in the Turkish economy before Covid 19 are not heartwarming anyway. While the Turkish economy was waiting for an opportunity to recover, it was caught by Covid 19.

The devastating economic effects of Covid 19 have emerged in the form of human deaths, increase in unemployment, loss of welfare, increase in budget deficits and public debt, deterioration in the finances of social security institutions, increase in current account deficit, decrease in official reserves and increase in exchange rates.

Human Deaths Covid 19 spread all over the world in the first half of 2020, causing more loss of life and economic destruction in developed countries. Based on the top 20 economies as a limitation, as of March 2, 2021, 10 of the 20 largest economies were ranked in the top ten and 14 were in the top 27 in the list of countries where the epidemic caused the most human deaths. China, S. Korea and Australia were separated from other countries by the low number of deaths (Worldometer, 2021). Since the epidemic did not start at the same time in all countries, the ranking could change over time. As can be seen in Table 1, the USA is far ahead in terms of death toll. Of the total 2,550,296 human deaths worldwide (Worldometer, 2021), about 20.7% occurred in the USA ($527,226 / 2,550,296 = 0.207$). Brazil, Mexico, India, England, Italy, France and Russia followed this country in terms of death toll. Mexico, China, Italy, Australia, England, Germany, Indonesia, and Canada, in descending order of death toll by number of cases. The record in the ratio of the number of recovered people to the number of cases (97.6%) belongs to Saudi Arabia. This country was followed by India, Turkey, Japan, China, Canada, Germany, Switzerland and Australia. This rate remained at a very low level (6.87%) in France. The UK has the highest number of human deaths per million population (1,805). This country was followed by Italy, USA, Spain, Mexico, France and Brazil. The very low number of people (3 people) who died per million population in China, the country where the epidemic first started, has caused this country's statistics to be viewed with suspicion.

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Increase in Unemployment As the Covid 19 epidemic spread all over the world and people were restricted from leaving their homes, there was a shock pause in economic activity around the world. Production has decreased in all sectors except for a few sectors such as cologne, masks, protective overalls, cleaning products, cargo, courier and internet services, whose use has increased due to the epidemic. Production has almost stopped in the transportation, tourism and sports sectors related to human mobility, and in the sectors of events such as congresses, conferences, cinemas, theaters and concerts that require people to be together. As a natural consequence of the decrease in production, unemployment rates of countries have increased. Governments have tried to prevent the unemployment rate from increasing further by emphasizing that the epidemic is temporary and easing the cost of labor on employers.

Loss of Welfare Deaths due to Covid 19, failure to hold funeral ceremonies, the inability to share the grief of the relatives of the funeral, the restriction of people leaving their homes, the inability to hold events such as mass worship, weddings and marriages have led to social and psychological costs that cannot be measured with money. However, here we will focus on the loss of welfare caused by the decrease in income caused by the epidemic. Due to the epidemic, it is desired to maintain a distance of 1-2 meters between people according to the size of the risk, in many sectors such as transportation, tourism, hotel management, restaurant, sports, barber, hairdresser, home services, babysitting, congress, conference, theater, cinema, concert, wedding. production could not be made for months. Production in these sectors came to a complete halt in April and May, and could only be partially resumed in March and June. When the base year of 2015 is accepted (2015=100), the industrial production index was 113.9 in March 2020, when the first sign of the epidemic appeared, and decreased to 78.1 in April. The capacity utilization rate in the manufacturing industry was 75.3% in March 2020 and decreased to 61.6% in April (HMB, 2020: 37, 45). Education services have turned into distance education via the internet. Generally, compulsory needs were tried to be met, and needs such as durable consumer goods, furniture and automotive were postponed.

Budget Deficits and Increase in Public Debt In order to reduce the damage caused by the epidemic in the business world, entrepreneurs and laborers had to be supported with public

resources. Due to the contraction in economic activity, the public finance balance deteriorated, budget deficits and debt stock increased. As stated above, the difficult conditions of the Turkish economy in 2018 and 2019 had a negative impact on the central government budget cash balance. With the effect of the Covid 19 epidemic, the budget balance deteriorated more in 2020. The central government budget cash deficit, which was -88.465 million TL in 2018, increased to - 124.556 million TL in 2019 and to -172,798 million TL in 2020.

Deterioration in the Finances of the Social Security Institution The high level of unemployment, underemployment, efforts to minimize layoffs, and encouragement to return to normal work led to an increase in the expenditures of the social security institution (SGK) and the deterioration of its financial structures. During the Covid 19 process, 3.5 million people were given short-time working allowance in the period of March-7 November 2020; 32.8 billion TL was spent within the scope of cash wage support, normalization support and unemployment benefit (Milliyet, 7.11.2020). As can be seen in Table 6, the SSI financial balance, which deteriorated before the epidemic, deteriorated more during the epidemic (year 2020). The deficit, which was -15,751 million TL in 2018, increased to 39,945 million TL in 2019 and increased by 51% to -60,418 million TL in 2020.

Increase in Current Account Deficit Current account is an important indicator of the productivity and global competitiveness of economies. The larger the figures of the transactions in the account, especially as a ratio to GDP, the more open the country is. The fact that the plus and minus accounts are equal or the plus accounts are high indicates that the global competitiveness of the economy is high. A large negative account creates a strong signal that borrowing and interest rates will increase. As seen in Table 7, while Turkey's current account gave a surplus of 9.649 million dollars in the January-October period of 2019, it had a deficit of -31,055 million dollars in the January-October period of 2020, when Covid 19 was experienced. Deficit exports were driven by a decrease in services revenue and primary revenue.

Decline in Official Reserves and Increase in Exchange Rate Official reserves first decreased rapidly when the epidemic started, then followed a fluctuating course. As seen in Figure 1, official reserves, which were 102,467 million dollars in February, decreased to 86,343 million dollars in April and reached their lowest value in September with 79,680 million dollars. TL/1Dollar rate increased continuously in the January-May 2020 period. The exchange rate, which was 1 \$ = 5.93 TL in January, increased to 6.96 TL in May, decreased to 6.82 TL in June, then increased continuously to 8.02 TL in November.

6. Conclusion

As a result, it is clearly seen that Covid 19 has negatively affected human psychology, social events have increased, the economy has come to a sudden halt all over the world, and negative developments in the economy are increasing day by day in today's world. The Covid-19 pandemic has affected the way people experience interpersonal relationships. The curfew was described as a different organization of daily life, with the increase in time spent at home and the reduction of distance through digital devices. This period was also seen as an evolution in the concept of empathy and produced new perspectives in examining the phenomenon from sociological and neurological perspectives. The neuro-sociological perspective analyzes the mechanisms involved in the empathic process and focuses on human communication and interpersonal relationships (Singer & Lamm, 2009; Decety & Ickes, 2009).

7. Resources

Alvarez, F., Argente, D., and Lippi, F. (2020). A simple planning problem for Covid-19 lockdown. *Covid Econ.* 14, 1–33. doi: 10.3386/w26981

APS (2020). Psychologists' welcome health fund telehealth support of Australians' mental health during COVID-19 outbreak. Australia: Australian Psychology Society at Tratto.

Baylor, C., Burns, M., McDonough, K., Mach, H., and Yorkstona, K. (2019). Teaching Medical Students Skills for Effective Communication with Patients Who Have Communication Disorders. *am. J. Spe. lang. pathol.* 28, 155–164. doi: 10.1044/2018_ajslp-18-0130

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- Cai, H., Tu, B., Ma, J., Chen, L., Fu, L., Jiang, Y., et al. (2020). Psychological impact and coping strategies of frontline medical staff in Hunan between January and March 2020 during the outbreak of coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID19) in Hubei. *china Med. sci. monit.* 2020:26. doi: 10.12659/MSM.924171
- CSTS (2020). Immediate Psychological Responses and Associated Factors during the Initial Stage of the 2019 Coronavirus Disease (COVID-19) Epidemic among the General Population in China. *int. J. Environ. pic. Pub Health* 17:1729. doi: 10.3390/ijerph17051729
- Durkheim, E. (1922). *Education and Sociology*. Milan: Ledizioni.
- Kang, L., Ma, S., and Chen, M. (2020). Impact on mental health and perceptions of psychological care among medical and nursing staff in Wuhan during the 2019 novel coronavirus disease outbreak: A cross-sectional study. *Brain Behav. Immun.* 87, 11–17. doi: 10.1016/j.bbi.2020.03.028
- Kawohl, W., and Nordt, C. (2020). COVID-19, unemployment, and suicide. *Lancet Psych.* 7, 389–390. doi: 10.1016/s2215-0366(20)30141-3
- Lai, J., Ma, S., Wang, Y., Cai, Z., Hu, J., Wei, N., et al. (2020). Factors Associated with Mental Health Outcomes Among Health Care Workers Exposed to Coronavirus Disease 2019. *JAMA Network Open* 3:e203976. doi: 10.1001/jamanetworkopen.2020.3976
- Li, S., Wang, Y., Yang, Y., Lei, X., and Yang, Y. (2020). Analysis of influencing factors of anxiety and emotional disorders in children and adolescents during home isolation during the epidemic of novel coronavirus pneumonia. *chin J. Child Heal* 2020, 1–9.
- Mache, S., Vitzthum, K., and Klapp, B. (2012). Stress, health, and satisfaction of Australian and German doctors—a comparative study. *World Hosp Health* 48, 21–27.
- Mamun, MA, and Griffiths, MD (2020). First COVID-19 suicide case in Bangladesh due to fear of COVID-19 and xenophobia: Suicide prevention strategies. *Asian J. Psych.* 51:102073. doi: 10.1016/j.ajp.2020.102073

- Mantovani, G. (1995). *Comunicazione e Identità: dalle situazioni quotidiane agli ambienti virtuali*. Bologna: il Mulino.
- Mazza, C., Ricci, E., Biondi, S., Colasanti, M., Ferracuti, S., Napoli, C., et al. (2020). Nationwide Survey of Psychological Distress among Italian People during the COVID-19 Pandemic: Immediate Psychological Responses and Associated Factors. *Int. J. Environ. Res. Public Health* 17:3165. doi: 10.3390/ijerph17093165
- Miles, S. (2014). *Kaci Hickox: Public Health and the Politics of Fear*. *Tratto da Bioethics*. Available online at: <http://www.bioethics.net/2014/11/kaci-hickox-public-health-and-the-politics-of-fear/> (accessed June 2, 2020).
- Mohindra, RRR, Suri, V., Bhalla, A., and Singh, SM (2020). Issues relevant to mental health promotion in frontline health care providers managing quarantine/isolated COVID19 patients. *Asian J. Psych.* 51:102084. doi: 10.1016/j.ajp.2020.102084
- Øyane, NPS, Elisabeth, M., Torbjørn, A., and Bjørn, B. (2013). Associations between night work and anxiety, depression, insomnia, sleepiness, and fatigue in a sample of Norwegian nurses. *PLoS One* 2013:e70228. doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0070228
- Prensky, M. (2012). What ISN'T Technology Good At? Empathy for One Thing! *Educ. Technol.* 52:64.
- Rana, W., Mukhtar, S., and Mukhtar, S. (2020). Mental health of medical workers in Pakistan during the pandemic COVID-19 outbreak. *Asian J. Psych.* 51:102080. doi: 10.1016/j.ajp.2020.102080
- Stoll, J., Müller, J., and Trachsel, M. (2020). Ethical Issues in Online Psychotherapy: A Narrative Review. *Front. Psych.* 10:993. doi: 10.3389/fpsy.2019.00993
- Suler, J. (2004). The Online Disinhibition Effect. *Cyb. Psychol. Behav.* 7, 321–326. doi: 10.1089/1094931041291295
- Tosoni, S. (2004). *Identità virtuali: comunicazione mediata da computer e processi di costruzione dell'identità personale*. Milan: Franco Angeli.
- Weir, K. (2020). *Grief and COVID-19: Morning our bygone lives*.

Washington: American Psychological Association.

World Health Organization (2019). Emergency Global Supply Chain System (COVID-19) Catalog. Available online at: [https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/emergency-global-supply-chain-system-\(covid-19\)-catalogue](https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/emergency-global-supply-chain-system-(covid-19)-catalogue) (accessed June 10, 2020).

Xiao, H., Zhang, Y., Kong, D., Li, S., and Yang, N. (2020). The effects of social support on sleep quality of medical staff treating patients with coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19) in January and February 2020 in

China. *Med. sci. monit.* 26:e923549. doi: 10.12659/MSM.923549

Zaffina, S., Camisa, V., Monducci, E., Vinci, M., Vicari, S., and Bergamaschi, A. (2014). Disturbo post traumatico also stress in operator sanitari coinvolti in un incidente rilevante avvenuto in ambito ospedaliero. *La Med. Del Lav.* 105:2014.

Zhou, X., Snoswell, CL, and Harding, LE (2020). The Role of Telehealth in Reducing the Mental Health Burden from COVID-19. *telemed. EHealth.* 26, 377–379. doi: 10.1089/tmj.2020.0068